

(2H, s, CH aromatic), 6.90 (2H, d, CH aromatic), 6.93 (2H, d, CH aromatic), 3.98 (6H, s, OCH₃), 3.90 (6H, s, OCH₃) and 10.95 (2H, s, NH); *m/z* (R=3,4-dimethoxyphenyl) 323, 162, 160, 137, 131, 116, 107, 101, 93 and 89.

Similarly, other Schiff bases were prepared (Table 1).

1,4 Bis(2'-aryl-5'(H)-4'-thiazolidinone-3'-ylamino) phthalazine (3): A mixture of thioglycolic acid (0.01 mol) and 1,4-bis(substituted benzalhydrazino)-phthalazine (0.01 mole) was refluxed for 10 h on an oil-bath at 110°–20°. It was then cooled and washed with sodium bicarbonate. The resulting solid was dried and recrystallised from methanol-dioxane (1 : 1), (52%), *m p* 130° (Found : C, 56.70; N, 13.19; S, 9.94. C₃₀H₃₀N₆O₆S₂ requires : C, 56.78; N, 13.25; S, 10.09); ν_{\max} (KBr) (R=3,4-dimethoxyphenyl) 3 250 (NH), 1 680 (C=O) and 685 cm⁻¹ (C-S-C); *m/z* 307, 258, 204, 161, 129, 102, 101, 89, 75, 47 and 44.

Similarly, other 4-thiazolidinones were prepared (Table 1).

TABLE 1 – PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS

Sl. no.	R	Schiff bases	4-Thiazolidinones
		M.p. °C	M.p °C
1.	Phenyl	150	low m.p.
2.	2-Chlorophenyl	145	low m p.
3.	4-Chlorophenyl	182	140(d)
4.	2,6-Dichlorophenyl	211	190
5.	3,4-Dichlorophenyl	180	180
6.	3-Aminophenyl	300	145(d)
7.	4-Aminophenyl	225(d)	310(d)
8.	2-Hydroxyphenyl	137	205
9.	4-Hydroxyphenyl	208	260(d)
10.	2-Methoxyphenyl	112	110
11.	4-Methoxyphenyl	160	115(d)
12.	3,4-Dimethoxyphenyl	184	130
13.	3-Methoxy-4-hydroxy-phenyl	115(d)	220
14.	3-Nitrophenyl	175	110(d)
15.	Cinnamyl	140	240(d)
16.	4-Dimethylaminophenyl	160	90

Antimicrobial activity: 4-Thiazolidinone derivatives were screened for antibacterial and antifungal activities using cup-plate⁴ method. The testing was carried out at a concentration of 100 µg using gram-positive bacteria *Staphylococcus aureus*, *S. citreus* and gram-negative bacteria *Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas fluores* and fungi *Candida albicans* and *Aspergillus flavus*. Most of the compounds showed moderate activity (zone of inhibition=14–22 mm) against different strains of bacteria and fungi.

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Synthesis and Antimicrobial Activity of 2-(3'-Chloro-4'-aryl-2'-azetidion-1'-yl)-4-(2"-methyl-4"-hydroxy-5"-isopropylphenyl)thiazoles

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IN view of the powerful antibiotic activity shown by β -lactams¹ and wide-range therapeutic activity shown by thiazole derivatives², we have undertaken the synthesis of 2-azetidiones bearing thiazole moiety of the type 2 by the action of chloro acetyl chloride on Schiff bases (1) in the presence of basic catalyst. The structures of the compounds have been supported by elemental analysis, ir, pmr and mass spectral data. The compounds have been screened for their antimicrobial activity.

4-Acetocthymol³ is obtained by condensing thymol to Frie's migration reaction in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride using nitrobenzene as solvent, which on condensation with thiourea in presence of iodine gives 2-amino-4-(2'-methyl-4'-hydroxy-5'-isopropylphenyl)thiazole⁴. This on further reaction with different aromatic aldehydes in presence of methanol yields Schiff bases (1a-t).

NOTES

Compounds **1** on treatment with chloroacetyl chloride and triethyl amine in dioxane yield the azetidinones (**2a-t**) (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

Antimicrobial activity: The compounds were screened for antibacterial and antifungal activity using cup-plate⁵ method at a concentration of 50 µg using gram-positive bacteria *Staphylococcus*

aureus and *S. citreus*, gram-negative bacteria *Escherichia coli* and *Pseudomonas fluorescens* and fungi *Candida albicans* and *Aspergillus niger*. Most of the compounds were found moderately active (15–25 mm zone of inhibition) against all the organisms. Ampicillin was taken as a standard drug which showed 13–22 mm inhibition under similar condition.

Experimental

All the melting points were determined in open capillaries and are uncorrected. The IR spectra was taken on Shimadzu 435-IR spectrophotometer and mass was taken on a spectrometer.

2-(Benzalamino-4-(2'-methyl-4'-hydroxy-5'-isopropylphenyl)thiazole (1a): A mixture of 2-amino-4-(2'-methyl-4'-hydroxy-5'-isopropylphenyl)thiazole (0.001 mol) and benzaldehyde (0.001 mol) in methanol (20 ml) was refluxed on a water-bath for 1 h. The resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol, (65%), m.p. 115° (Found: C, 71.13; H, 5.96; N, 8.29. C₂₀H₂₀N₂OS requires: C, 71.39; H, 5.99; N, 8.32%); ν_{max} (KBr) 1610 (C=N), 700 (C-S-C of thiazole) and 1510 cm⁻¹ (C=C); m/z 337 (M+1), 336 (M⁺), 249, 233, 207, 206, 189, 177, 133, 105, 91 and 77.

Similarly, other Schiff bases (1b-t) were prepared (Table 1).

2-(3'-Chloro-4'-aryl-2'-azetidinon-1-yl)-4(2'-methyl-4'-hydroxy-5'-isopropylphenyl)thiazole (2): A mixture of **1** (0.005 mol, 1.682 g) and triethylamine (0.005 mol, 0.5 ml) in dioxane (30 ml) was

TABLE 1 - PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 1 AND 2*

Compd.	R	Schiff base (1a-t)			2-Azetidinone (2a-t)		
		Mol. formula	M.p. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula	M.p. °C	Yield %
a	Phenyl	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ N ₂ OS	115	65	C ₂₂ H ₂₁ ClN ₂ O ₂ S	193	66
b	4-Hydroxyphenyl	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₂ S	194	68	C ₂₂ H ₂₁ ClN ₂ O ₂ S	169	62
e	2-Methoxyphenyl	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₂ S	188	62	C ₂₃ H ₂₃ ClN ₂ O ₂ S	145	72
d	3-Methoxyphenyl	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₂ S	223d	69	C ₂₃ H ₂₃ ClN ₂ O ₂ S	178	68
e	4-Methoxyphenyl	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₂ S	138	68	C ₂₃ H ₂₃ ClN ₂ O ₂ S	159	70
f	3,4-Dimethoxyphenyl	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₂ S	102	65	C ₂₄ H ₂₅ ClN ₂ O ₂ S	182	64
g	2-Chlorophenyl	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ ClN ₂ OS	140	68	C ₂₂ H ₂₁ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₂ S	238	65
h	4-Chlorophenyl	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ ClN ₂ OS	142	70	C ₂₂ H ₂₁ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₂ S	153	68
i	2,4-Dichlorophenyl	C ₂₀ H ₁₅ Cl ₂ N ₂ OS	104	71	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₂ S	142	64
j	2,6-Dichlorophenyl	C ₂₀ H ₁₅ Cl ₂ N ₂ OS	101	69	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₂ S	172	61
k	3,4-Dichlorophenyl	C ₂₀ H ₁₅ Cl ₂ N ₂ OS	174	74	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₂ S	156	57
l	3-Aminophenyl	C ₂₀ H ₂₁ N ₂ OS	108	76	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ ClN ₂ O ₂ S	160	70
m	4-Aminophenyl	C ₂₀ H ₂₁ N ₂ OS	122	68	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ ClN ₂ O ₂ S	300d	74
n	2-Nitrophenyl	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₂ S	112	62	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ ClN ₂ O ₂ S	197	68
o	3-Nitrophenyl	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₂ S	131	65	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ ClN ₂ O ₂ S	218	63
p	4-Dimethylaminophenyl	C ₂₂ H ₂₅ N ₂ OS	173	59	C ₂₄ H ₂₆ ClN ₂ O ₂ S	300	71
q	Cinnamyl	C ₂₂ H ₂₃ N ₂ OS	111	60	C ₂₄ H ₂₅ ClN ₂ O ₂ S	218d	62
r	Vanilline	C ₂₁ H ₂₃ N ₂ O ₂ S	115	65	C ₂₃ H ₂₅ ClN ₂ O ₂ S	155	66
s	Furyl	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ N ₂ O ₂ S	142d	61	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ ClN ₂ O ₂ S	198	65
t	2-Hydroxynaphthyl	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ N ₂ O ₂ S	118	54	C ₂₆ H ₂₃ ClN ₂ O ₂ S	108	59

*All compounds gave satisfactory N analysis.

stirred well with gradual addition of chloroacetyl chloride (0.005 mol, 6 ml) at 50–60° for 10–12 h and left at room temperature for 3 days. Excess of solvent was then distilled off and the resulting solid was crystallised from 95% ethanol, (66%), m.p. 193° (Found: C, 63.76; H, 5.11; N, 6.76. $C_{23}H_{21}ClN_2O_2S$ requires: C, 63.99; H, 5.12; N, 6.78%); ν_{max} (KBr) 1680 (C=O), 700 (C–Cl), 1400 (C–N), 700 (C–S–C) and 3450 cm^{-1} (OH); m/z 363, 324 (base peak), 308, 248, 232, 206, 189, 177, 133, 105, 103, 91, 77, 68, 56 and 43.

Similarly other 2-azetidinone derivatives (2b–t) were prepared (Table 1).

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Synthesis and ^{13}C Nmr Study of 3-Aryloxymethyl-6-aryl-(7H)-s-triazolo[3,4-b][1,3,4]thiadiazines

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IN continuation of our studies on the synthesis of new s-triazolothiadiazines as potential anthelmintic agents^{1,2}, we now report the synthesis of 3-aryloxymethyl-6-aryl-(7H)-s-triazolo[3,4-b][1,3,4]thiadiazines (3) by the interaction of 3-aryloxymethyl 4-amino-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazoles¹ (1) with α -bromo-substituted-acetophenones (2)

A mixture of 1 (0.01 mol), 2 (0.01 mol) and pyridine (1.2 cm^3) was refluxed in absolute alcohol (50 cm^3) for 4 h. Alcohol was then distilled off and the residue treated with cold dilute hydrochloric acid, washed with water and filtered. The resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol (Table 1).

The ir spectra (KBr) of 1 displayed bands due to 1,2,4-triazoles at 3230, 2720, 1635, 1570 and 1470 cm^{-1} . In addition, strong intensity band at 1250–1200 cm^{-1} and medium intensity band at 1070–1000 cm^{-1} due to aromatic ether

TABLE 1 - PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 3

Compd. no.	R	R ₁	Yield %	M.p. °C	Mol. formula
3a	H	H	65	132	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₃
b	H	CH ₃	71	186	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₃
c	H	Cl	75	154	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ ClN ₄ O ₃
d	CH ₃	H	68	220	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₃
e	CH ₃	CH ₃	64	202	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₃
f	CH ₃	Cl	72	172	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ ClN ₄ O ₃
g	Cl	H	74	168	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ ClN ₄ O ₃
h	Cl	CH ₃	70	183	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ ClN ₄ O ₃
i	Cl	Cl	75	166	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ Cl ₂ N ₄ O ₃

linkage^{3,4} were obtained. The absence of carbonyl frequency at 1725–1705 cm^{-1} , (further confirmed by ^{13}C nmr spectra) and SH stretching vibrations at 2600–2550 cm^{-1} confirmed the cyclic structure 3.

The ^{13}C nmr spectrum (CDCl₃) of 3d showed signals due to 18-carbon atoms in the molecule. The signals due to carbons (C=N) at C-3, C-4 and C-6 positions were observed at 141.6, 150.4 and 154.0 ppm respectively. The methylenic carbon C-2, methyl carbon C-1 and the (7H) carbon C-5 showed signals at 59.6, 23.6 and 24.9 ppm respectively. The 3-aryloxy aromatic carbons showed signals at 158.3, 115.5, 129.1 and 133.5 ppm due to C-1'; C-2',6'; C-3',5' and C-4' respectively. The 6-aryl aromatic carbons showed signals at 115.1, 127.4, 129.6 and 121.8 ppm due to C-1''; C-2'',6''; C-3'',5'' and C-4'' respectively.

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